

FEINBERG – INDELIBLE MODEL IN UZBEK LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

This article is about a Russian poet who was born and raised in Uzbekistan, who worked side by side with the people of this country throughout his life and made a great contribution to the development of the country. Along with information about his life and creative heritage, the article also contains unique opinions of the great writer and poet Alexander Feinberg.

Introduction. There are people in life who leave an indelible mark on the human mind. There are billions of images on Earth, but each of them has its own inner world. It is as if they never repeat each other like pieces of snow. There are figures who discover the human heart with their lines, and they are endowed with a great ability by God. These talented people, called poets, express the feelings and experiences of people in beautiful forms through their works of art.

One of such talented people is the poet, translator, screenwriter Alexander Feinberg. The poet, whose childhood was spent in the difficult years of World War II, was born in 1939 in Tashkent. His name and work are valuable to Uzbek readers and lovers of poetry. His works reflect the kindness, generosity and kindness of the Uzbek people.

The main results and findings. The poet graduated from the Faculty of Journalism of Tashkent State University (now the National University of Uzbekistan) in 1965. From 1965 to 1969 he worked as a consultant in the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan. Dozens of collections of poetry have been published in Tashkent, Moscow and St. Petersburg. In particular, in 1965 "Velotracks" and then "Etude" (1967), "Seconds" (1969), "Poems" (1977), "Far Bridges" (1978), "Answer" (1982), "Short wave" (1983), "Spread string" (1984), "Liberal sonnets" (1990), "Sheet" (2008). Alexander Feinberg is a member of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan. For several years he chaired the Seminar of Young Writers of Uzbekistan. Feinberg is a talented translator. He showed readers around the world that Uzbek artists have great skills and experience. The poet translated into Russian Erkin Vahidov's epic "Ruhlar isyoni" (Rebellion of Spirits), poems by Abdulla Aripov, Omon Matchon, Sirojiddin Sayid, Khosiyat Rustamova. He made a great contribution to the publication of Alisher Navoi's works in Russian. Feinberg's poems have appeared in Smena, Yunost (Youth), Noviy Mir (New World), Zvezda Vostoka (Eastern Star), Novaya

Volna (New Wave) magazines, and in the United States, Canada, and Israel. published in the periodicals of a number of foreign countries, such as. "Just as the sun, the air, the earth, and the water nourish all living things, so the life of the people inspires the writer. The more talented the writer, the more experienced the penman, the more the people will be grateful to him, the more he will respect his work and literature in general," said Abdullah Qahhor. Feinberg's great contribution to the development of Uzbek literature was appreciated by our government, and the honorary titles of "Honored Cultural Worker of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and "People's Poet of Uzbekistan" were awarded as a sign of our boundless respect for this great man. In 2004, the poet was awarded the Pushkin Medal by the Decree of the President of Russia. The poet in his poem "Star":

*Each star has a turn,
Every dream and intention will be answered.
The singing lamp wanders in the sky,
Of course, every light shines in time.
It rises and the sea jumps on the rock,
I land on the shore the wind blows salt.
As long as I live, the planetary lamp,
Burn a star for me in the sky.*

- he wrote. Undoubtedly, Alexander Feinberg became one of the brightest stars in the sky of Uzbek poetry. His works are deeply rooted in the hearts of literary lovers. Screenwriter is an important part of Feinberg's work. On the basis of his screenplay, the Uzbekfilm studio shot films "Under the hot sun", "My brother", "Healed in Kandahar", "Criminals and acquittals" at the Tajikfilm studio and a number of other films. He is also the author of more than twenty cartoons. Well-known Uzbek poet Abdulla Aripov describes Feinberg as follows: "As for the work of Alexander Feinberg, not all high-sounding words reflect even a hundred percent of the truth, because he was in fact a unique poet and translator. No other world-class, Russian-speaking writer can sing such a heartfelt song to our sunny land". Don't bother for me, I am living proudly. My shoulder is a constant confidence, Bright days are in front of me - a trigger. Conclusion The poet died in 2009 in Tashkent. The charm of Feinberg's poetry, the philosophy of his works, the clarity of feelings and sincerity were able to capture the hearts of people of different ages, attitudes and views. He lived and created in our heavenly country. The clear sky, fresh air and clear waters of this country became a source of inspiration for him. This is manifested in all its beauty in the warm, colorful lines of the poet.

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